

TYPES OF VIOLENCE AND BEHAVIOURAL APPROACH TO CONTROL VIOLENCE IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract

Violence occurs at three levels, these are mind, speech and action level. Violence at mind level is called internal or intent violence while the one done at speech or body level is called external violence. The behavioral approach to control violence consists of treating others the way we want others to treat us. If we want the people to treat us nicely, we must treat them in the nicest way. Be, what you want. Be non-violent and the world will be non-violent to you. The head of institution should be peace-loving or non-violent if he wants to maintain peace in his organization. One should resolve that none should be hurt through the medium of mind, words and actions even to the slightest extent. One should ask for forgiveness if one has hurt inadvertently.

Key words: *Violence, Non-Violence, Behavioral Approach.*

Introduction

Violence has become almost a way of life. It is prevalent all over, be it homes, offices, factories or even educational institutions. Daily we listen about strikes as well as murders or suicides in educational institutions. Such happenings may be due to prevalence of frustration in the lives of the youth. Students are not getting the treatment which they are entitled to. In the other

article, Sharma (2013) thrower some light on the spiritual approach to control violence. She stressed on the fact that we are all one as our creator (God) is one; He is sitting in all of us in the form of soul or spirit. It shows that there is hardly any scope for violence; paradoxically it is occurring. It was considered worthwhile to supplement the spiritual approach. In this article, an attempt has been made to supplement the spiritual approach with the behavioural approach to control violence especially in the educational institutions.

Root Cause of Violence

It is the attachment or hatred in our minds responsible for the violence. It is a common observation that when we come across someone who agrees with our dictations, opinions or ideas we become friendly with him and get attached to him. On the other hand if one does not agree with us we develop hatred towards him. This is the main reason behind the creation of rivalry groups in institutions. Such groups are engaged in letting down others. When our desires are not met, anger or restlessness occurs and this in turn leads to unimaginable actions which may put a student behind bars and spoil their career. It must be kept in mind that each individual is bestowed with mind and intellect by virtue of which he has opinions. It is very rare that one's opinion may match with others in all the spheres of life. Some have peace loving minds while some lose their temper even on very trivial matters. It is the status of our mind or intellect that controls our thoughts and process of desires.

Type of violence

Internal violence

Violence occurs at three levels: mind, action and speech levels. There are three models through which violence takes place. Internal violence deals with the violence at mind level. Our mind has five passions:

- a) Lust / Desires
- b) Anger

- c) Greed
- d) Attachment
- e) Ego

All these five passions act as seeds for violence. Firstly, these passions create a strong feeling of violence with the self. They don't allow us to remain in peace. When we are full of desires, anger, greed, attachment and ego, how can we remain in peace. All these passions prevail upon mind to adopt unqualified actions to fulfill or satisfy them, causing mental tension. This mental disturbance kills so many useful micro-organisms in our body which are useful in digestion etc. by secreting useful enzymes. The students are not aware of the bacterial level of violence which is caused in the self itself. Likewise a desire for sex leads to violence as millions of sperms of semen are killed. All these sperms are living organisms and are potential human beings. The students should be aware of the magnitude of such killing of sperms. As such, they should avoid such violence. This would help them in maintaining their vigor as well as optimum health.

The acts done at mind level are considered as sins. Singh, C in his book mentioned about the teachings of Lord Christ wherein the Lord states that whoever looked upon a woman with lust after her hath committed adultery in the heart (Mathew 5:28). The sins are not visible to others and such cases can't be tried in the courts. At least one should be kind to himself and not pollute himself with such negative thoughts. This pollution of head is more dangerous and is leading to the environmental pollution. The students as well as other beings should resolve to maintain an inner intent not to hurt anyone even to the slightest extent.

External Violence

External violence refers to the violence done at speech and action level. To speak maliciously or utter negative words against a person in his absence is also considered violence. Abusing or speaking ill is quite common. Such

incidents may lead to murders or suicides etc. Apart from this, the mobiles and non-sense messaging is leading to a lot of violence. It is quite common in schools, colleges and universities. The alcohol and drug intake are also becoming common and further aggravating the problem of violence. It is worth mentioning that to prepare one drop of alcohol, millions of bacteria are killed. As such, the responsibility of killing this number of micro-organisms (lives) lies on the alcohol consumers. The students taking alcohol must be aware of killings at this magnitude. It is also a crime though a hidden one.

Non-violence means peace. Peace means 100% concentration which is also a pre-requisite for studies. The violence attacks the intellect which in turn loses its discriminating power to distinguish between right and wrong deeds. Loss of this power leads to ugly incidents and students have to repent for these later. Violence is another name of tension which causes loss of memory. Because of tension, students forget the answers in examinations but soon after the examination they may remember what they were finding so difficult to recall at that time.

Both the intent and external violence are dangerous and lead to spoilage of careers of students. So let us pray to God to provide us the required strength to fulfill our commitment to non-violence through mind, speech and body level. If we are non-violence the world would also be non-violent to us.

Behavioural Approach to control violence

None should suffer in any way. For this, we must know how to be with oneself. If we want love, be loving, if we want care, be caring, if we want peace, be peaceful, if we want joy, be joyful (Holden, 2007). If we demand acceptance from others, be accepting. It is literally to become what we want. If we want honesty, be honest, if we want loyalty, be loyal; if we want trust, be trusty; if we want non-violence, be non-violent and if we want courage, be courageous. Be what you want in life and you will be rewarded accordingly.

One should treat others the way he wants others to treat him. This is a law of cause and effect or law of proportionate returns (Schuller, 2001). If you are critical of others, you will be criticized. If you want people to treat you nicely, treat them nicely. The kinder you are to others, the more kindness you are likely to receive back. If the head of institution wants non-violence in his institution he should be non-violent. The same vibrations will reach to other staff and students as well. Vibrations move faster than the words.

In spite of all this, if one abuses somebody, it would definitely hurt the other person. The natural response of any person would be to hurl the abuse back to the person from where it originated. But before doing so one must think about the hurt his abuse would cause to the other person. Before reacting, one must keep in mind that God resides in all living beings and hurting others amounts to hurting God. This the first sign of humanity which will stop violence (Amin 2005,2009). If someone hurts us, it is certain that we must have misbehaved with them in the past. It teaches one a great lesson that one must deposit the hurts in our own account. Forgive others and we will be definitely forgiven.

Forgiveness is an attribute of soul. Unless we accept the wholeness or complete or blissfulness of the soul, we will only be demanding from others, and all our relationships will be needy. When we identify ourselves with the soul or awaken the inherent qualities of soul, we become self-sufficient and self dependent. The identity, which is whole, perfect and infinite does not demand from others, rather fulfills the demands of others. The violence occurs only when we demand some things from others. The wholeness has no demands and it opens up itself to entirely different experience of loving relationships among all the faculties and students in a learning organization.

Dissolving of Ignorance

Due to ignorance, person is made to believe that his life is real and he is a permanent resident of this world. There is nothing real about it (Singh, 1967).

We can't take anything along with us after death. Just as the blossom does not last long, so does not life, we are simply the guests to this nature. The world or nature is feeding us with bounties of air, water and food. A guest does not insist on comforts of a house or its surroundings, apart from what the host offers. So does it befit us all to live in this world during our temporary stay (whatsoever may be the length of our stay be it 60, 70 or even 90 years) on this planet, resigned to the will of God and the provisions God has made for us. The will of God is manifested everywhere and everything is being taken care by Him. So we should live in acceptance for whatever period but without any reservation. When we start demanding that means we are practicing another form of violence by being greedy, therefore let us live as true guests of nature.

Conclusion

From above discussion it can be concluded that hurting others amounts to hurting God residing in all of us. Awakening to this right belief can help greatly in controlling violence especially in the educational institutions. Also make a strong resolve to never hurt anybody by words, actions or mind even to the slightest extent. Ask for forgiveness if someone is hurt by you inadvertently. By training students to develop this tolerance towards others we can surely be able to curb and control the menace of violence which is so wide spread.

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